

Figure 3b: the 5x5 vāstu, MY 4 y+10c-y+11b.

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|-----------|-----------|--------|
| 1 sun | 5 Jupiter | 9 ketu |
| 2 moon | 6 Venus | |
| 3 Mars | 7 Saturn | |
| 4 Mercury | 8 rāhu | |